

Thrombocytopenia in Neonatal Sepsis: A Prognostic and Early Diagnostic Indicator

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 26-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Neonatal sepsis is one of the most common cause of morbidity as well as neonatal mortality. Thrombocytopenia of varying severity is one of the common finding in neonatal sepsis which may be a predictor of adverse outcome**Material & Methods:** The present study is a hospital based study. A total of 50 neonates admitted in the Hospital with clinical diagnosis of sepsis during the study period were included. Platelet count and indices along with blood culture was done for the patients.**Results:** Thrombocytopenia of varying severity was noted in 100% cases of neonatal sepsis, of them, 68% had mild thrombocytopenia, whereas 22% and 10% cases had moderate and severe thrombocytopenia.**Conclusion:** Although blood culture is a gold standard method for diagnosis of sepsis, utility of platelet count in neonatal sepsis should be observed carefully as it was sterile in certain neonates. Platelet indices and platelet count may aid in early diagnosis of sepsis and determining the prognosis and severity of sepsis. However, platelet count and platelet indices such as Mean Platelet Volume, Platelet Distribution Width and Plateletcrit (PCT) are not associated with neonatal risk factors and organism responsible for neonatal sepsis.**Keywords:** Neonatal Sepsis, Thrombocytopenia, Platelet Indices.

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Introduction

The term neonatal sepsis is used to define a clinical syndrome in neonates (0 –28 days) characterized by systemic signs of infection and confirmed by isolation of bacterial pathogens from the blood stream.[1] Neonatal sepsis can be categorized as early onset sepsis (developing within 72 hours of birth) and late neonatal sepsis (developing between 72 hours and 28 days of birth).[2] Neonatal sepsis is one of the most common cause of neonatal morbidity attributing to majority of NICU admissions.[3] Neonatal sepsis (including septicemia, meningitis, pneumonia, arthritis, osteomyelitis and urinary tract infections) is the second most common cause of neonatal mortality worldwide.

Neonatal sepsis may be due to bacterial, fungal, viral, protozoal as well as rickettsial infections.[7] Group B streptococci are the most common organism responsible for neonatal sepsis globally, whereas in India, predominant causative agents include gram negative organisms.[8] The neonate

with sepsis may present with nonspecific symptoms such as hypo/hyperthermia, lethargy, poor feeding, bradycardia, hypotonia, apnea, respiratory distress or metabolic derangements.[9] Blood culture is most important tool which is helpful in establishing the definitive diagnosis of neonatal sepsis. Blood culture can be utilized to identify the organism responsible for neonatal sepsis and to identify the sensitivity pattern of these organisms.[10]

Thrombocytopenia i.e. platelet count less than $150 \times 10^9/L$ is one of the most common hematological abnormality observed in neonatal period. Thrombocytopenia has been documented in approximately 18 to 35% of neonates admitted in NICU, for various causes. However, thrombocytopenia is reported in higher proportions of neonates with extremely low birth weight (birth weight ≤ 1000 g).[11-13] Severe thrombocytopenia may be associated with clinically significant bleeding among neonates due to decrease platelet

count. Literature suggests that neonates with gram positive or gram negative septicaemia usually present with rapidly progressive thrombocytopenia and lowest platelet counts are reached in 1-2 days of onset.[14,15] Thrombocytopenia has been suggested as an independent risk factor for neonatal mortality in very low birth weight neonates with sepsis.[19] Such associations between thrombocytopenia and sepsis related complications and mortality have also been established in adults with sepsis.[20] Thus, the prognostic value of thrombocytopenia in neonatal sepsis need to be evaluated. Severe thrombocytopenia with bleeding tendency is common in neonates with sepsis and may be an important predictive factor for assessing the risk of mortality in such cases.

Material and Methods

The present study is a hospital based prospective study conducted in the Department of Pathology in collaboration with Department of Paediatrics and Microbiology of People's College of Medical Sciences & Research Centre, Bhopal, Madhya Pradesh over a period of 18 months.

A total of 50 neonates admitted in the Hospital with clinical diagnosis of sepsis during the study period were included in the study.

Inclusion Criteria: All full term neonates with clinical diagnosis of septicemia and admitted to NICU during the study period with consent from the parents or guardian were selected using convenient sampling.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Mother with History suggestive of ITP, SLE / other autoimmune disorder, on medication during pregnancy (sulfonamides, quinine / quinidine, thiazides, tolbutamide, vancomycin, hydralazine, and heparin)
- Neonates with history suggestive of bleeding disorder in family, trisomies.
- Conditions associated with sequestration of platelets.
- Culture proven sepsis either because of suspicion of contamination, missing data on blood culture.

Data Collection Procedure:

The following neonatal data was recorded using questionnaire-

- 1) Gestational age,
- 2) Birth weight,
- 3) Small for gestational age (SGA, defined as a birth weight below the 10th centile for gestational age),
- 4) Very low birth weight (VLBW, defined as a birth weight below 1500 gram),

- 5) Gender
- 6) Day of onset and Duration of symptoms,
- 7) Occurrence of severe hemorrhage,
- 8) Use of platelet transfusions,
- 9) Occurrence of intravascular thrombosis (defined as the detection of a vascular thrombosis on ultrasound examination),
- 10) Length of hospital stay and
- 11) Neonatal mortality.

The following maternal data was recorded- Maternal hypertension.

Maternal hypertension is defined "as a diastolic blood pressure of 90 mm Hg or more on two occasions more than four hours apart, or a single diastolic blood pressure above 110 mm Hg".

Blood samples were collected with all septic precautions in EDTA & blood culture vials. Samples were transported to respective laboratories for platelet count, indices and blood culture as soon as possible.

The following hematologic parameters were recorded for each neonate:

- Platelet count at onset of sepsis and the lowest count during entire episode of sepsis.
- Different platelet indices such as Plateletcrit, Mean platelet volume (MPV), Platelet distribution width (PDW) were studied.

Thrombocytopenia is defined as platelet count $< 150 \times 10^9/L$

Thrombocytopenia was classified as

- Mild ($101-149 \times 10^9/L$),
- Moderate ($51-100 \times 10^9/L$),
- Severe ($21-50 \times 10^9/L$) Or
- Very Severe ($\leq 20 \times 10^9/L$).

Blood culture

Blood samples from the suspected neonates were collected under all aseptic precautions in BHI(Brain heart Infusion) broth and processed in laboratory as per standard microbiological procedure.

Blood culture was done using 2 methods i.e.

- 1) Automated Method
- 2) Manual Method - Media glucose broth

Organism isolated from blood culture was subjected to identification and antibiotic susceptibility by CLSI guidelines.

The primary outcome of this study was occurrence of thrombocytopenia in neonatal sepsis. Secondary outcomes was the severity and duration of

thrombocytopenia, as well as the occurrence of severe haemorrhage and mortality in neonates.

Statistical Analysis: Ms Excel was used to compile data and IBM SPSS Software version 20 was used to analyse. Categorical data was represented as frequency and proportion whereas continuous data was represented as mean and standard deviation. Occurrence of thrombocytopenia was expressed as proportion. Association of thrombocytopenia with various factors was assessed using chi square test. P value less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Observations and Results: The present study was conducted in a total of 50 neonates admitted in NICU during the study period with the clinical diagnosis of sepsis.

The findings are as follows

- In present study, 26(52%) neonates with sepsis were male & 24(48%) cases were females.
- Mean gestational age of neonates was 37.2 ± 2.13 weeks. Majority of neonates were term neonates (>37 weeks of gestation) whereas about 21(42%) cases were preterm neonates.
- Neonates were categorized into early and late neonate depending upon the age of neonate. 27(54%) neonates presented in early neonatal period (<7 days).
- About 8(16%) cases with sepsis were low birth weight (<2.5 kg) and remaining 42 (84%) cases were normal weight neonate.
- Out of 50 neonates with sepsis, active bleeding was documented in 7(14%) cases in our study.
- Table 1 - Distribution according to platelet count- Platelet indices in the neonates admitted with sepsis. Mean initial platelet was $112.12 \pm 28.32 *10^3/mm^3$ whereas lowest platelet count was $95.34 \pm 26.33 *10^3/mm^3$.
- Table 2- Distribution according to severity of thrombocytopenia- Thrombocytopenia of varying severity was noted in 100% cases of neonatal sepsis, of them, 68% had mild thrombocytopenia, whereas 22% and 10% cases had moderate and severe thrombocytopenia.
- Table 3- Association of severity of thrombocytopenia with neonatal characteristics- The present study documented no significant association of thrombocytopenia with neonatal characteristics such as gestational age, gender and birth weight ($p > 0.05$).
- Table 4- Association of Bacterial culture with MPV, PDW and Plateletcrit- The present study observed no significant association of bacterial culture with platelet indices such as MPV, PDW as well as plateletcrit ($p > 0.05$).
- Fig 1- Distribution according to bacterial culture- Bacterial culture revealed staph aureus in majority of cases 30(60%), followed by E coli and Klebsiella in 6(12%) and 4(8%) cases respectively. However, culture was sterile in 5(10%) cases.
- Fig 2- Association of bacterial culture with thrombocytopenia -Mean initial platelet count as well as lowest platelet count were lower in cases with Enterobacter and highest in sterile cases. However, we observed no significant association of bacterial culture with both initial and lowest platelet count ($p > 0.05$).
- Fig 3-Association of bacterial culture with severity of thrombocytopenia-Majority of cases with neonatal sepsis were associated with staphylococcus aureus irrespective of severity of thrombocytopenia. The observed association between thrombocytopenia and bacterial culture was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 1: Distribution according to platelet Parameters

Platelet indices	Mean	SD
Initial platelet count($*10^3/mm^3$)	112.12	28.32
Lowest platelet count ($*10^3/mm^3$)	95.34	26.33
Mean Platelet Volume (fl)	9.53	0.92
Platelet Distribution width (fl)	15.02	1.84
Plateletcrit (%)	0.24	0.03

Table 2: Distribution according to severity of thrombocytopenia

Thrombocytopenia	Frequency (n=50)	Percentage
Mild	34	68.0
Moderate	11	22.0
Severe	5	10.0

Table 3: Association of severity of thrombocytopenia with neonatal characteristics

Variables		Mild	Moderate	Severe	χ^2	P value
Age (days)	0-7	20 (58.8)	6 (54.5)	1 (20)	2.6	0.27
	8-28	14 (41.2)	5 (45.5)	4 (80)		
Gender	Male	18 (52.9)	7 (63.6)	1 (20)	2.66	0.26
	Female	16 (47.1)	4 (36.4)	4 (80)		
Gestational age (weeks)	<37	16 (47.1)	4 (36.4)	1 (20)	1.49	0.47
	>37	18 (52.9)	7 (63.6)	4 (80)		
Birth weight (kg)	<2.5	6 (17.6)	2 (18.2)	0 (0)	1.29	0.86
	2.6-3	24 (70.6)	8 (72.7)	4 (80)		
	>3	4 (11.8)	1 (9.1)	1 (20)		

Table 4: Association of Bacterial culture with MPV, PDW and Plateletcrit

Bacterial culture	MPV		PDW		Plateletcrit	
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD
E.coli	9.55	0.81	14.55	1.22	0.25	0.03
Enterobacter	10	0.92	15.9	0.76	0.24	0.03
Group B Streptococcus	9.6	0.57	15	1.98	0.23	0.007
Klebsiella	9.73	0.85	16.2	2.06	0.24	0.03
S. Aureus	9.4	0.97	15.02	1.94	0.25	0.03
Sterile	9.7	1.18	14.06	2.01	0.24	0.02
ANOVA	0.29		0.83		0.39	
P value	0.91		0.54		0.85	

Figure 1: Distribution according to bacterial culture

Figure 2: Association between bacterial culture and platelet count

Figure 3: Association between bacterial culture and severity of thrombocytopenia

Discussion

Neonatal sepsis is one of the most common cause of morbidity as well as neonatal mortality. Neonatal sepsis not only affect the immediate health, but is an important determinant of the growth and development of the affected neonate.[3] Worldwide, neonatal sepsis represents second most common cause contributing to neonatal mortality.[4] Literature suggest a link of neonatal sepsis and thrombocytopenia, i.e. low platelet count ($150 \times 10^9/L$). The platelet count as well as other platelet indices such as Plateletcrit, Mean platelet volume, Platelet distribution width are components of complete blood picture, which is the basic, easy available investigation conducted in all the neonates admitted with sepsis. Bacterial culture is utilized as an effective tool for establishing the definitive diagnosis and identifying the organism and their sensitivity pattern of these organisms. [10]

Roberts IA et al (2003) documented that thrombocytopenia in neonates is one of the commonly observed finding, which is mild in majority of cases and resolve spontaneously.[24] The exact pathogenesis of thrombocytopenia in neonatal sepsis is not known but has been linked with endothelial damage leading to activation of reticulo-endothelial system and destruction of platelets. Apart from this, decreased production is also observed in neonates due to lower proportions of marrow megakaryocytes, low thrombopoietin concentrations. The consumption of platelets in the initial phase of sepsis is also high due to inflammation and immune mediated mechanisms. [15-18]

In our study all the cases with neonatal sepsis had low platelet count at the time of admission, which further decreased during the course of treatment. Mild, moderate and severe thrombocytopenia was observed in 68%, 22% and 10% cases of neonatal sepsis. Mean initial platelet count in neonates were 112.12 ± 28.32 ($\times 10^3/mm^3$) whereas the lowest count recorded in neonates were 95.34 ± 26.33 ($\times 10^3/mm^3$). Thrombocytopenia was noted in 39.5% cases in a study by Gupta BK et al (2019), majority of cases had mild followed by moderate and severe thrombocytopenia.[28] Nandyal SS et al (2016) documented thrombocytopenia of varying severity in 99 out of 155 cases of neonatal sepsis. Mild and moderate thrombocytopenia was noted in 17.1% neonates each, about 65.6% cases had severe thrombocytopenia.[25] In another study by Bhat et al (2018), the authors observed initial thrombocytopenia in 84 (58.7%) cases, of them, 39.3% were mild, 25% were moderate and 35.7% were severe.[27]

Severe thrombocytopenia may be associated with bleeding tendencies in neonates with sepsis and

bleeding tendencies have been identified as an important predictive factor of mortality. In our study active bleeding was noted in 14% neonates and thus these neonates were managed using platelet transfusion apart from routine and emergency neonatal care. Andrew M et al (1987) highlighted the importance of thrombocytopenia and its management in cases with neonatal sepsis. They suggested that platelet must be transfused in neonates with severe thrombocytopenia in order to diminish the occurrence and severity of hemorrhages.[23]

Saber AM et al (2021) also documented that case of severe neonatal thrombocytopenia require more platelet transfusion and are at high risk of mortality.[29]

Depending upon the duration at onset of sepsis, neonatal sepsis is categorised as early neonatal sepsis (<72 hours) and late neonatal sepsis (>72 hours). The causative organism as well as the prognosis depends upon time of sepsis. Early onset sepsis is secondary to maternal causes whereas late onset sepsis is due to environmental factors. In present study, majority i.e. 54% neonates belonged to early neonatal age (<7 days). Mean age of neonates with sepsis was 9.3 ± 5.3 days. We observed no significant association of age of neonate at the time of sepsis (early or late neonatal sepsis) with severity of thrombocytopenia.

Simonsen KA et al (2014) documented that male neonates have higher risk of meningitis or sepsis, most commonly with gram-negative enteric bacilli.[21] In our study, majority of neonates with sepsis were males (52%). Though severity of thrombocytopenia was higher in females with neonatal sepsis, but our study observed no significant association of gender with severity of thrombocytopenia ($p > 0.05$).

Gestational age is documented as one of the important determinant of neonatal mortality in presence of neonatal sepsis.[5,6] In our study, about 42% neonates were preterm, who were delivered before 37 weeks of gestations and mean gestational age of neonates was 37.2 ± 2.13 weeks. However, our study observed no significant association of severity of thrombocytopenia with gestational age ($p > 0.05$).

Apart from gestational age, birth weight of neonate is also an important determinant of neonatal morbidity and mortality.[5,6] Mean birth weight of neonates was 2.8 ± 0.2 kg and about 16% neonates were low birth weight. The present study documented no significant association of birth weight with severity of thrombocytopenia.

Platelet indices are considered as an important biomarkers which represent platelet activation and they have both diagnostic as well as prognostic

values. We included MPV, PDW and PCT apart from platelet count as they are components of CBC. These counts have clinical utility in patients with sepsis.[22] In our study mean platelet volume was 9.53 ± 0.92 fl, whereas mean platelet distribution width and plateletcrit was 15.02 ± 1.84 fl and $0.24 \pm 0.03\%$ respectively in cases with neonatal sepsis. These findings were supported by Mittal A et al (2018), in which the authors documented increased PDW and MPV in neonatal sepsis cases as compared to normal neonates.[26]

Blood culture is the gold standard method for diagnosis of neonatal sepsis, but the results take time to appear. Blood culture is helpful in establishing definitive etiological diagnosis, identify the organism and assess the sensitivity pattern of these organisms.[10] In our study, Blood culture was positive in 90% cases and staphylococcus aureus was the most common etiological agent associated with neonatal sepsis (60%), followed by E coli (12%).

We aimed to assess the association of thrombocytopenia and other platelet indices with various pathogens. Though all the cases with severe thrombocytopenia were associated with staphylococcus aureus, we observed no significant association of severity of thrombocytopenia with bacterial culture ($p > 0.05$). Also, mean initial platelet count and lowest platelet count were lowest in Enterobacter and highest in sterile cases of neonatal sepsis, the observed association was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$). MPV was highest in Enterobacter cases, PDW and Plateletcrit was highest in Klebsiella, but the observed association of platelet indices with bacteria responsible for sepsis was statistically insignificant ($p > 0.05$)

Conclusion

Neonatal sepsis is common condition which is a significant contributor of neonatal morbidity and mortality. It is essential to identify neonatal sepsis early as neonates are vulnerable population in which sepsis not only increase the mortality but has significant impact on neurological development of child. Thrombocytopenia of varying severity is one of the common finding in neonatal sepsis which may be predictor of adverse outcome. Though blood culture is gold standard method for diagnosis of sepsis, its utility in neonatal sepsis should be observed carefully as it was sterile in certain neonates.

Platelet indices and platelet count may aid in early diagnosis of sepsis and determining the prognosis and severity of sepsis. However, platelet count and platelet indices such as Mean Platelet Volume, Platelet Distribution Width and Plateletcrit (PCT) are not associated with neonatal risk factors and organism responsible for neonatal sepsis.

Ali et al.

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